

The Late Jōmon Ainu words for colors and their Proto-Sino-Tibetan counterparts

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Abstract

Late Jōmon Ainu (LJA) terms for colors have clearly seen Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST) correspondences. LJA “black”, “dark” **kur* correlates to PST **γVm(H)* “dark”, “shade”. LJA word for “green” / “blue” – **siw-ni-ʔun* literally means “of bitter wood” (*siw-ni* means “bitter wood” – *Picrasma quassioides*), the stem here is **siw* “bitter”. LJA **siw* correlates with PST **sř(H)* “yellow”, with PST **TiŋH* “green”, “black”, with PST **Cij* – a kind of grass (*Tribulus terrestris*), also, the PST the form for “bitter”, “pungent” is **cVp*. LJA “red” **hure* correlates with PST **H^wVr* “red”. LJA “white” **retar* is a compound of two roots: *re* that correlates with PST **rěw(H)* “heat”, “burn”, and *tar* that correlates with PST **tār* “a kind of cloth”, i.e., *re-tar* originally meant “fabric made of nettle”. Fabric made of nettle is of white-gray in color; therefore, the word for “white” was derived from the name of the fabric.

Keywords: Ainu language; Sino-Tibetan languages; Ainu-Minoan stock; Sino-Caucasian family; comparative linguistics

1. Introduction

Earlier it was shown that the Ainu language is a relative of the Sino-Tibetan family. Ainu and Sino-Tibetan languages demonstrate notorious structural (Akulov 2016, Nonno 2025b, Nonno 2025c) and lexical similarities (Akulov 2026a, 2026b; Akulov, Nonno 2024, 2025a, 2025c, 2025b; 2026; Nonno 2025a).

Ainu is not a distant relative, but is a member of the Sino-Tibetan family, and Ainu is a relic of the Proto-Sino-Tibetan language (Akulov, Nonno 2026: 3 – 4).

Modern / historical Ainu dialects started to diverge in late Jōmon (about 1500 – 300 BCE) (see Nonno 2015: 64), and when we make reconstructions after modern Ainu dialects we receive forms of Late Jōmon Ainu (LJA) – the language that was the immediate ancestor of all modern Ainu dialects.

The current paper continues discovering concrete similarities between Ainu and the Sino-Tibetan languages. The current paper is devoted to discovering similarity between the Late Jōmon Ainu words for colors and their Proto-Sino-Tibetan (PST) counterparts.

The Ainu basically distinguished four colors: “black”, “green”, “red”, and “white”, and correspondingly in the Ainu language there are four words for denoting colors. And all existing colors are divided into four categories, for instance, blue, green, and yellow all belong to the same category and are denoted by the word meaning “green”; red, and orange colors belong

to another category and are marked by the word meaning “red”. A similar picture of rubrication of colors can also be seen in other ancient languages.

2. “Black”

2.1. The LJA word “black”

In Hokkaido Ainu there two forms for “black”, “dark”: *kunne* (Batchelor 1905: 250; Kayano 2005: 220; Ōta 2005: 105), and *ekurok* (Batchelor 1905: 101, Kayano 2005: 133, Ōta 2005: 34).

In Sakhalin Ainu the form for “black” is *kunne* (Dobrotvorskii 1875: 154), Dobrotvorskii recorded this word as *kunni* (in the Cyrillic orthography used by Dobrotvorskii – *кунни* [kunni]) (Dobrotvorskii 1875: 154), the variant *kunni* is just a distorted form of *kunne*.

And also in Sakhalin Ainu there is the form *ekurokh* (in the Cyrillic orthography used by Dobrotvorskii – *экурохъ* [ekuroh]), meaning “dark” (Dobrotvorskii 1875: 458),

In Kuril-Kamchatka Ainu the form for “black” is *ekurok* (Krasheninnikov 1994: 187), Krasheninnikov recorded this word as *ekuroko* (in the Cyrillic orthography used by Krasheninnikov – *экуроко* [ekuroko]) (Krasheninnikov 1994: 187), *ekuroko* is just a distorted form of *ekurok*.

The form *kur* / *kuri* means “shadow”, “cloud”, “dark” (Batchelor 1905: 251, Kayano 2005: 218, Ōta 2005: 106)

Ōta points out that the form *kunne* consists of two components: *kur* “shade”, “shadow” and copula *ne* (Ōta 2005: 105).

The form *kunne* that is represented in modern / historical Ainu dialects evidently is a result of later positional assimilation ($C_1C_2 \rightarrow C_2C_2$) that could be due to a certain influence of the Japanese language, and originally this form had the view of *kur ne*.

As far as the root *kur* “black”, “dark” is represented in all Ainu dialects, so it is possible to reconstruct for LJA the form **kur* for “black”.

2.2. LJA **kur* and its PST correspondence

LJA **kur* “black”, “dark” correlates well with PST **γVm(H)* “dark”, “shade”.

For our conclusions about resemblance of two word-forms would be less speculative, we calculate the degree of resemblance of the compared forms.

The method of calculation of degree of resemblance is described in Nonno 2025a: 52 – 53; Akulov, Nonno 2025a: 6 – 7; Akulov, Nonno 2025b: 7 – 9.

As far as V in **γVm* is not specified, so we can reconstruct any vowel for this V, and in the current case we can reconstruct [u].

LJA [kur] ~ PST [γum]

$$[k] \sim [ɣ] = (\text{voiceless velar plosive consonant}) \sim (\text{voiced velar fricative consonant}) = (2/4 + 2/4)/2 = 0.5$$

$$[u] \sim [u] = 1.$$

$$[r] \sim [m] = (\text{voiced alveolar flap consonant}) \sim (\text{voiced bilabial nasal consonant}) = (2/4 + 2/4)/2 = 0.5$$

$$[kur] \sim [ɣum] = (0.5 + 1 + 0.5)/3 \approx 0.66.$$

For the sake of illustration and in order to get a threshold of the degree of similarity demonstrated by word for colors in related languages we now compare the English word *red* [red] with Spanish word *rojo* [roxo] “red” which are cognate and both originated from Proto-Indo-European **h₁rewd^h* “red”¹.

$$[\text{red}] \sim [\text{roxo}]$$

$$[r] \sim [r] = 1;$$

$$[e] \sim [o] = (\text{high-mid front unrounded vowel}) \sim (\text{high-mid back rounded vowel}) = (3/5 + 3/5)/2 = 0.6;$$

$$[d] \sim [x] = (\text{voiced alveolar plosive consonant}) \sim (\text{voiceless uvular fricative consonant}) = (1/4 + 1/4)/2 = 0.25;$$

The second [o] of [roxo] has no counterpart in [red], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero.

$$\text{And thus, } [\text{red}] \sim [\text{roxo}] = (1 + 0.6 + 0.25 + 0)/4 \approx 0.46.$$

The degree of similarity of LJA **kur* and PST **ɣum* is higher than the degree of similarity of English *red* and Spanish *rojo*. The fact that forms of LJA and PST demonstrate such value of the degree of similarity which is usually demonstrated by words for colors of languages belonging to the same family means that LJA and PST are related. Along with previously demonstrated facts it means that the Ainu language is related to the Sino-Tibetan family, and that Ainu is a relic of the Proto-Sino-Tibetan language.

2.3. The LJA and PST word “black” / “shade” is cognate with the word “man” / “person”

It's quite remarkable fact that the LJA root for “black” – **kur* looks exactly like the LJA word for “person” / “human being” – **kur*². The PST counterpart of LJA **kur* “person” is the form **kur*³ and it correlates well with the above-considered PST form for “shade” – **ɣum* (**ɣVm*).

How did it happen that the forms for “man” and “black” coincided? This is not a coincidence. This is a relic of very ancient times. Very ancient ancestors of modern Ainu were dark-skinned

¹ Wiktionary 2026.

² Akulov, Nonno 2024: 27.

³ Akulov, Nonno 2024: 27.

and the simplest and most obvious example of black color was human skin. The word "human being" / "person" appeared first, and then appeared the word "black".

The same situation can be seen in the Proto-North Caucasian language where **l'włĚ* / **l'włV* "person", "man"⁴ and **l'Haχ_V* "black"⁵.

The North Caucasian languages belong to the Ainu-Minoan stock (Akulov 2018, 2021).

And also the same can be seen, for instance, in Sumerian. Within the Sumerian language⁶ there were two sociolects: *eme-gir* and *eme-sal* (where *eme* means "language"). *Eme-sal* is a feminine sociolect, while *eme-gir* is the standard Sumerian, literally it means "the language of people", i.e., the Sumerians, and, hence, the form *gir* is a word meaning "man". And the Sumerian word for "black" is *gig*⁷.

This fact is interesting for understanding the worldview of ancient peoples: they perceived the world through the prism of the human body.

Modern races began to form after the end of the last ice age (which ended around 12,000 BC). And as recently as about 10,000 years ago, all people were dark-skinned yet. Thus, certain concepts of ancient languages preserved relics of ancient worldview.

3. "Green" / "blue"

3.1. The LJA word "green" / "blue"

In Hokkaido Ainu dialects the word meaning "green", "blue", "yellow" is *siwnin* (Ōta 2005: 204). Batchelor also gives this word in the form *shiunin* (Batchelor 1905: 424).

In the dictionary of Sakhalin Ainu compiled by M. M. Dobrotvorskii the word for "green" is *shiunin* (in the Cyrillic orthography used by Dobrotvorskii this word is recorded as *шиунинь* [ʃiunin]), this is just a distorted form of the word *siwnin*.

In the word-list of Kuril-Kamchatka Ainu compiled by S.P. Krasheninnikov the word for green is *teuninua* (in the Cyrillic orthography used by Krasheninnikov this word is recorded as *теунинуа* [teuninua]). The form *teuninua* evidently is a distorted form *siwnin* with the particle *wa* marking the end of a sentence.

Thus, it is possible to state that the LJA form for "green" is **siwnin*.

However, it is important to note that the form *siwnin* evidently is connected with the form *siw-ni* literally "bitter wood" *Picrasma ailanthoides* or *Picrasma quassioides* (Batchelor 1905: 424, Ōta 2005: 204).

The form *siwnin* literally means "of bitter wood", it is possible to state that originally the form had the following view: **siw-ni-ʔun*.

And thus, the stem here is **siw*.

It is currently unclear why the LJA word "green" comes from the name of *picrasma*, and not, for example, simply from the word "grass", *picrasma* is actually no greener than any other

⁴ Starostin 2005b.

⁵ Starostin 2005a.

⁶ Sumerian also belongs to the Ainu-Minoan stock (Akulov 2022).

⁷ Wikipedia 2026c.

plants, but it is the fact that the LJA word "green" was derived from the LJA designation for picrasma.

Fig.1. *Picrasma quassioides* (image source – Wikipedia 2026b)

3.2. Comparing LJA **siw* with PST counterparts

The LJA form **siw* correlates with PST **sīr(H)* "yellow"⁸, with PST **TiŋH* "green", "black"⁹. And also, with PST **Cj̄j* – a kind of grass (*Tribulus terrestris*)¹⁰.

Also, it is important that in PST the form for "bitter", "pungent" is **cV̄p* (Starostin 2005d).

The PST form **cV̄p* "bitter" evidently is related to PST forms **sīr(H)* "yellow", and **TiŋH* "green".

3.2.1. LJA **siw* and PST **sīr(H)*

We suppose that it is more correct to state that [r] in the form **sīr(H)* is actually voiced alveolar flap – [r̄].

⁸ Starostin 2005g.

⁹ Starostin 2005j.

¹⁰ Starostin 2005c.

The form $s\bar{r}(H)$ is a compact recording of the following forms: $s\bar{r}H$ and $s\bar{r}$.

The sign H here marks an unidentified voiceless consonant of laryngeal group, so we suppose that the form $s\bar{r}H$ can be rewritten as $s\bar{r}h$.

3.2.1.1. LJA $*siw$ and PST $s\bar{r}h$

LJA [siw] ~ PST [s̄rh]

[s] ~ [s̄] = 1;

[i] ~ [ī] = (high front unrounded vowel) ~ (high central unrounded long vowel) = $(3/4 + 3/5) = 0.675$;

[w] ~ [r] = (voiced labial–velar approximant consonant) ~ (voiced alveolar flap consonant) = $(2/5 + 2/4)/2 = 0.45$;

[h] of [s̄rh] has no counterparts in [siw] so in this case the degree of similarity is zero.

Thus, [siw] ~ [s̄rh] = $(1 + 0.675 + 0.45 + 0)/4 \approx 0.53$. This degree of similarity is higher than the degree of similarity of words [red] and [roxo] that is 0.46.

3.2.1.2. LJA $*siw$ and PST $s\bar{r}$

LJA [siw] ~ PST [s̄r]

[s] ~ [s̄] = 1;

[i] ~ [ī] = (high front unrounded vowel) ~ (high central unrounded long vowel) = $(3/4 + 3/5) = 0.675$;

[w] ~ [r] = (voiced labial–velar approximant consonant) ~ (voiced alveolar flap consonant) = $(2/5 + 2/4)/2 = 0.45$.

LJA [siw] ~ PST [s̄r] = $(1 + 0.675 + 0.45)/3 \approx 0.71$.

This degree of similarity is significantly higher than the degree of similarity of words [red] and [roxo] that is 0.46.

3.2.2. LJA $*siw$ and PST $*Ti\eta H$

The PST form $*Ti\eta H$ “green”, “black” is a compact recording of the following forms: $*Ti\eta$ and $*Ti\eta H$.

The sign T here marks an unidentified voiceless consonant of alveolar – alveolo-palatal group, and thus, we suppose that it is possible to write here [t] instead T.

The sign H here marks an unidentified voiceless consonant of laryngeal group, so we suppose that it is possible to write here [h] instead H.

Thus, we have two forms: $*ti\eta$ and $*ti\eta h$

3.2.2.1. LJA $*siw$ and PST $*ti\eta h$

[siw] ~ [tiŋh]

[s] ~ [t] = (voiceless alveolar fricative consonant) ~ (voiceless alveolar plosive consonant) = $(\frac{3}{4} + \frac{3}{4})/2 = 0.75$;

[i] ~ [i] = 1;

[w] ~ [ŋ] = (voiced labial-velar approximant consonant) ~ (voiced velar nasal consonant) = $(\frac{3}{5} + \frac{3}{4})/2 = 0.675$;

[h] of [tiŋh] has no counterparts in [siw], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero.

[siw] ~ [tiŋh] = $(0.75 + 1 + 0.675 + 0)/4 \approx 0.6$.

This value of the degree of similarity is higher than the degree of similarity demonstrated by words [red] and [roxo] that is 0.46.

3.2.2.2. LJA *siw and PST *tiŋ

[siw] ~ [tiŋ]

[s] ~ [t] = (voiceless alveolar fricative consonant) ~ (voiceless alveolar plosive consonant) = $(\frac{3}{4} + \frac{3}{4})/2 = 0.75$;

[i] ~ [i] = 1;

[w] ~ [ŋ] = (voiced labial-velar approximant consonant) ~ (voiced velar nasal consonant) = $(\frac{3}{5} + \frac{3}{4})/2 = 0.675$.

[siw] ~ [tiŋh] = $(0.75 + 1 + 0.675)/3 \approx 0.81$.

This value of the degree of similarity is significantly higher than the degree of similarity demonstrated by words [red] and [roxo] that is 0.46.

3.2.3. LJA *siw and PST *Cij

In the PST form *Cij the sign C expresses an unidentified consonant, and thus, it is possible to state that C was [s].

LJA [siw] ~ PST [sij]

[s] ~ [s] = 1;

[i] ~ [i] = (high front unrounded vowel) ~ (high front unrounded short vowel) = $(\frac{4}{4} + \frac{4}{5})/2 = (1 + 0.8)/2 = 0.9$;

[w] ~ [j] = (voiced labial-velar approximant consonant) ~ (voiced palatal approximant consonant) = $(\frac{3}{5} + \frac{3}{4})/2 = 0.675$;

Thus, $[siw] \sim [sij] = (1 + 0.9 + 0.675)/3 \approx 0.86$.

This value of the degree of similarity is significantly higher than the degree of similarity demonstrated by words [red] and [roxo] that is 0.46.

3.2.4. LJA **siw* and PST **cV̄p*

As far as the sign \bar{V} marks an unidentified long vowel, so it is possible to reconstruct here long [i]

LJA [siw] ~ PST [cīp]

$[s] \sim [c] = (\text{voiceless alveolar fricative consonant}) \sim (\text{voiceless palatal plosive consonant}) = (2/4 + 2/4)/2 = 0.5$;

$[i] \sim [\bar{i}] = (\text{high front unrounded vowel}) \sim (\text{high front unrounded long vowel}) = (4/4 + 4/5)/2 = 0.9$;

$[w] \sim [p] = (\text{voiced labial-velar approximant consonant}) \sim (\text{voiceless bilabial plosive consonant}) = (2/5 + 2/5)/2 = 0.4$.

LJA [siw] ~ PST [cīp] = $(0.5 + 0.9 + 0.4)/3 = 0.6$.

This value of the degree of similarity is higher than the degree of similarity demonstrated by words [red] and [roxo] that is 0.46.

4. "Red"

The LJA word for "red" is **hure* and the corresponding PST form is **H^wVr* (Akulov, Nonno 2024: 27).

The sign H in the form **H^wVr* marks an unidentified voiceless consonant of laryngeal group, so we suppose that it is possible to write here [h] instead H.

And the sign V in **H^wVr* expresses an unidentified vowel, so we can reconstruct any vowel for this V, and in the current case we can reconstruct [u].

The PST word "red" can be represented as **h^wur*.

The PST word *h^wur* "red" is possibly connected with the PST word **ʔ^wij* "blood"¹¹.

LJA [hure] ~ PST [h^wur]

$[h] \sim [h] = 1$;

[^w] has no counterparts in [hure], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero;

$[u] \sim [u] = 1$;

$[r] \sim [r] = 1$;

[e] of [hure] has no counterparts in [h^wur], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero.

$[hure] \sim [h^wur] = (1 + 0 + 1 + 1 + 0)/5 = 0.6$.

¹¹ Starostin 2005k.

This degree of similarity is higher than that of [red] and [roxo] which is 0.46. It means that forms **hure* and **H^wVr* definitely can be cognates.

5. “White”

5.1. The LJA word “white”

In Hokkaido Ainu dialects the word “white” is *retar* (Kayano 2005: 476; Ōta 2005: 178). In the dictionary of Hokkaido Ainu compiled by Jh. Batchelor the word “white” is *retara* (Batchelor 1905: 376), the form *retara* is just the form *retar* distorted by the influence of the Japanese language: under the influence of Japanese language Ainu CVC syllables converted into CVCV syllables.

In the dictionary of Sakhalin Ainu compiled by M. M. Dobrotvsorskii the word for “white” is *tetara* (in the Cyrillic orthography used by Dobrotvsorskii this word is recorded as *memapa* [tetara]). This form is just a local variant of the form *retar*: the Ainu /r/ can optionally be realized as [d] / [t], and converting of CVC syllable *tar* into CVCV *tara* is a result of influence of the Japanese language.

In the word-list of Kuril-Kamchatka Ainu compiled by S.P. Krasheninnikov the word for “white” is *retanoo* (in the Cyrillic orthography used by Krasheninnikov this word is recorded as *ретаноо* [retanoo]) (Krasheninnikov 1994: 187). The form *retanoo* evidently is a distorted variant of the form *retar*.

And, thus, it is possible to state that the LJA form for “white” is **retar*.

5.2. Comparing LJA **retar* with PST **th(r)Vŋ*

LJA **retar* “white” can be compared to PST **th(r)Vŋ* “clear”, “pure”¹². We suppose that the form **th(r)Vŋ* actually can be rewritten as **thrəŋ*.

If we compare LJA **retar* with PST **thrəŋ* supposing the inversion of consonants (Fig. 2), we receive the following:

[retar] ~ [thrəŋ]

[r] ~ [r] = 1

[e] ~ [ə] = (high-mid front unrounded vowel) ~ (mid central unrounded vowel) = $(3/5 + 3/4)/2 = 0.675$;

[t] ~ [t] = 1;

[h] of [thrəŋ] has no counterparts in [retar], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero;

[a] of [retar] has no counterparts in [thrəŋ], so in this case the degree of similarity is zero;

the final [r] of [retar] can be compared with [ŋ]:

[ŋ] ~ [r] = (velar voiced nasal consonant) ~ (voiced alveolar flap consonant) = $(2/4 + 2/4)/2 = 0.5$.

¹² Starostin 2005i.

And thus, [retar] ~ [thrəŋ] = (1 + 0.675 + 1 + 0 + 0 + 0.5) / 6 ≈ 0.53. This degree of similarity is higher than that of [red] and [roxo] which is 0.46. It means that forms **retar* and **thrəŋ* definitely can be cognates.

Fig. 2. Scheme representing the inversion that is supposed to have place between forms **retar* and **thrəŋ*

However, there are two principal obstacles against the possibility of such collation.

First, the inversion supposed above is highly improbable taking into the account the fact that in previous comparisons of LJA and PST forms there are no examples of such transformations.

Second, the fact that the word “white” is supposed to be connected with the word “clear” is actually quite improbable since such association is very abstract while in the thinking of ancient people was very figurative, i.e., the concept of “white” should have been derived from a certain concrete item, not from an abstract idea of “clear”.

We suppose that the LJA word “white” – **retar* is a compound of two roots: *re* and *tar*.

The root *re* can be compared with PST form **rěw(H)* “heat”, “burn”¹³, and also with PST **rě* “rope”¹⁴. The root *re* in this context denotes nettle, i.e., nettle could be was denoted after its main features: nettle is well known as a stinging herb and also nettle was quite a wide spread material for manufacturing of ropes. The PST form **rěw(H)* “heat”, “burn” correlates well to the Ainu word *ari* “to burn”, “to kindle”¹⁵.

Ōta Mitsuru writes that the word-form *ari* (he records it as *are*) is actually causative of the verb “to sit” – *a-re* where *a* is singular stem of the verb “to sit”, and *-re* is one of standard causative suffixes. And according to this logic, to kindle a fire literally means “to seat a fire” (Ōta 2005: 7). However, we suppose that the word-form *ari* / *are* is not a causative, but is a form connected with PST **rěw(H)* “heat”, “burn”.

¹³ Starostin 2005f.

¹⁴ Starostin 2005e.

¹⁵ Kayano 2005: 38.

In this case took place the same transformation as, for instance, in the case of numeral “three”: basically the Ainu root meaning “three” is *re*, but in compounds it becomes *ar*, for instance *ar-wan* “seven” literally “ten without three”¹⁶. The ending *-i* in *ari* can be just a result of late influence of Japanese, under which Ainu syllables of VC became VCV structures.

The root *tar* can be compared with PST form **tār* meaning “a kind of cloth”¹⁷. The PST form **tār* correlates well with Ainu *tara* “rice bale”, “straw bag”¹⁸.

It is quite noteworthy that the Japanese word that is used by Kayano as an equivalent of the Ainu word *tara* is the word 俵 *tawara* (the reading *tawara* is the kun-yomi of the sign 俵).

According to one explanation, the Japanese word *tawara* originally was a compound of the following words: *ta* 田 “field” and *wara* 藁 “straw”. According to another explanation the word *tawara* is a compound of verb *tawamu* 撓む “to bend”, “to flex”, “to bold” and *wara* 藁 “straw”, and thus, *tawara* means “bent straw”. The fact that there are different versions of the etymology of the word *tawara* suggests that it does not have a clear unambiguous etymology.

Also, it is noteworthy that in the Okinawan language the word “straw bag” 俵 is *tāra* [ta:ra]¹⁹. The Okinawan form *tāra* looks exactly like the Ainu word *tara*.

The Okinawan language is known as one of Japonic idioms (along with the Hachijō dialect) preserving some very archaic features. And thus, it is possible to state that Okinawan *tāra* is closer to the original than Japanese *tawara*.

We suppose that Japanese *tawara* and Okinawan *tāra* originated from Ainu *tara*, and first in the Ancient Japanese language the word *tara* had the meaning “rough fabric”, and later in the Japanese language this word was rethought so it would become closer to the word *wara* “straw”.

The fact that Okinawan language better preserves the word originated from LJA correlates well with the fact that Okinawan and Ainu people demonstrate notorious resemblance in the aspect of physical anthropology (Hanihara et al 1993).

Although ethnicity is determined not by genetics or physical anthropology, but by the primary language, but languages are spread by people, so when it comes to the relationship between two languages or long-term contact, there must be traces of contact between the two populations, which can be detected by population genetics and physical anthropology. In modern conditions cultural phenomena can be spread through web and media without actual direct contacts of the corresponding populations, but if the matter is about ancient epochs and we see that some ancient languages / cultures have a common origin or certain common features that indicate long-term contacts between two peoples, then physical anthropology and / or population genetics should demonstrate certain traces of contacts or a common origin of the two corresponding populations.

Summarizing all said in this paragraph, it is possible to state that the LJA word-form **retar* “white” is a compound of two roots: *re* + *tar*, where *re* means “stinging herb” or “the herb which is used for manufacturing of ropes” (i.e. nettle), and *tar* means “fabric” / “clothing”.

And thus, the form *re-tar* originally meant “fabric made of nettle”.

¹⁶ Tamura 2000: 254.

¹⁷ Starostin 2005h.

¹⁸ Kayano 2005: 297.

¹⁹ Jlect 2026.

Fabric made of nettle fibers is more white-gray in color, unlike, for example, fabric made of tree bast which has more yellowish / beige tint. Therefore, the word for “white” was derived from the name of the fabric.

In the culture of historical Ainu there were and are special clothes made of nettle fibers, these clothes are named *retarpe* literally “white thing” (see Fig. 3), and the color of *retarpe* differs from that of Ainu clothes made of tree bark fiber which is beige / yellowish (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. A retarpe (image source – Antiquities Dealers’ Association of America 2026)

Fig. 4. An attus (image source – Wikipedia 2026a)

Thus, the LJA form *retar should be compared not with PST *th(r)Vŋ “clear”, “pure”, but with the PST compound *rěw(H) “heat” + *tăr “a kind of cloth”.

The form *rěw(H)-tăr is a compact representation of the following two forms: *rěw-tăr and *rěwh-tăr

The degree of resemblance of LJA *retar and PST *rěw-tăr is the following:

[r] ~ [r] = 1;

[e] ~ [ě] = (high-mid front unrounded vowel) ~ (high-mid front unrounded short vowel) = $(4/4 + 4/5)/2 = 0.9$;

[w] has no counterparts in [retar], so in this case the degree of resemblance is zero;

[t] ~ [t] = 1;

[a] ~ [ă] = (low front unrounded vowel) ~ (low front unrounded short vowel) = $(4/4 + 4/5)/2 = 0.9$;

[r] ~ [r] = 1.

Thus, *retar ~ *rěw-tăr = $(1 + 0.9 + 0 + 1 + 0.9 + 1)/6 = 0.8$.

The degree of resemblance of LJA *retar and PST *rěwh-tăr is the following:

[r] ~ [r] = 1;

[e] ~ [ě] = (high-mid front unrounded vowel) ~ (high-mid front unrounded short vowel) = $(4/4 + 4/5)/2 = 0.9$;

[w] has no counterparts in [retar], so in this case the degree of resemblance is zero;

[h] has no counterparts in [retar], so in this case the degree of resemblance is zero;

[t] ~ [t] = 1;

[a] ~ [ă] = (low front unrounded vowel) ~ (low front unrounded short vowel) = $(4/4 + 4/5)/2 = 0.9$;

[r] ~ [r] = 1.

Thus, *retar ~ *rěwh-tăr = $(1 + 0.9 + 0 + 0 + 1 + 0.9 + 1)/7 \approx 0.68$.

Both values of the degree of resemblance received for the LJA form *retar and its PST counterparts are significantly higher than the degree of resemblance of [red] and [roxo] which is 0.46.

6. Conclusion

Terms for colors of Late Jōmon Ainu and their Proto-Sino-Tibetan counterparts demonstrate such values of the degree of resemblance, which are usually demonstrated by terms for colors of languages belonging to the same family. Along with previously demonstrated facts it means that the Ainu language is related to the Sino-Tibetan family, and that Ainu is a relic of the Proto-Sino-Tibetan language.

References

Akulov A. 2016. Ainu is a relative of Sino-Tibetan stock (preliminary notes). *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 2, № 2; pp.: 31 – 38

Akulov A. 2018. Ainu-Minoan stock. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 4, № 1; pp.: 2 – 25

Akulov A. 2026a. Comparing Late Jōmon Ainu “five” *ʔasik and “hand” *ʔaske with Proto-Tibeto-Burman “hand” *g-(t)syaw-k/ŋ. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 12, N 1; pp.: 40 – 45

Akulov A. 2026b. Late Jōmon Ainu “three” *re and Proto-Sino-Tibetan “three” *dVm (*dəm). *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 12, N 1; pp.: 46 - 51

Akulov A. 2021. Northeast Caucasian languages and the Ainu-Minoan stock. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 7, N 1; pp.: 2 – 8

Akulov A. 2022. Sumerian and the Ainu-Minoan stock. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 8, № 1; p.: 6 – 11

Akulov A., Nonno T. 2025a. Comparing Ainu kinship terms with their Sino-Tibetan counterparts (Part I). *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 11, N 3; pp.: 2 – 16

Akulov A., Nonno T. 2025b. Comparing Ainu numerals “one”, “two”, “three”, “four”, “five” with their Sino-Tibetan counterparts. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 11, N 2; pp.: 1 – 20

Akulov A, Nonno T. 2026. Comparing Late Jōmon Ainu terms for body parts with their Proto-Sino-Tibetan and Proto-Tibeto-Burman correspondences. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 12, N 1; pp.: 2 – 19

Akulov A., Nonno T. 2025c. Comparing the main Ainu kinship terms with their Sino-Tibetan counterparts (Part II). *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 11, N 4; pp.: 2 – 14

Akulov A., Nonno T. 2024. Some lexical correspondences between the Ainu language and the Sino-Tibetan family. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 10, N 1; pp.: 16 – 39

Antiquities Dealers’ Association of America. 2026. Ainu Retarpe (Nettle Fiber) Robe <https://adadealers.com/antiques/index.php?page=out&id=6819&cid=340> – accessed May 2026

Batchelor Jh. 1905. *An Ainu-English-Japanese dictionary: (including A grammar of the Ainu language)*. Tokyo: Methodist publishing house; London, K. Paul, Trench, Trübner, co.

Dobrotvorskii M. M. 1875. *Ainsko-russkii slovar’* (An Ainu-Russian dictionary). Izdatel’stvo Kazanskogi universiteta. Kazan’

Hanihara K., Hanihara T., Koizumi K. 1993. Biological Relationship between the Jomon-Ainu and Pacific Population Groups. *Japan Review*, No. 4 (1993), pp.: 7 – 25
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/25790923?seq=1> – accessed May 2026

Jlect 2026. たーら【俵】 taara <https://www.jlect.com/entry/6082/taara/> – accessed May 2026

Kayano Shigeru 萱野茂 2005. *Ainugo jiten* アイヌ語辞典 (Ainu language dictionary). Sanseidō, Tokyo

Krasheninnikov S. P. 1994. *Opisaniye zemli Kamchatka* (Kamchatka land description). Vol. II. Nauka, Saint Petersburg

Nonno T. 2025a. Comparing the system of Ainu personal pronouns with that of Qiang. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 11, N 1: pp.: 45 – 57

Nonno T. 2025b. Comparing the system of directional prefixes of Ainu with that of Qiang, *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 11, N 2; pp.: 39 – 43

Nonno T. 2015. Some preliminary thoughts on the structure of Late Jōmon Ainu language. *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 1, № 2; pp.: 64 – 67

Nonno T. 2025c. The etymology of the Ainu prohibitive marker *iteki*, *Cultural Anthropology and Ethnosemiotics*, Vol. 11, N 3; pp.: 41 – 45

Ōta Mitsuru 太田満 2005. *Asahikawa ainugo jiten* 旭川アイヌ語辞典 (A dictionary Ainu language of the Asahikawa dialect). Asahikawa, Ainugo kenkyūjō

Starostin S. A. 2005a. North Caucasian etymology database. Proto-North Caucasian *IHaχ_V (~ ʰ-) “black”

https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fdata%2fcauc%2fcaucet&text_number=171&root=config – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005b. North Caucasian etymology database. Proto-North Caucasian *l̥iwl̥Ě / *l̥iwl̥Ě “man”, “male”

https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fdata%2fcauc%2fcaucet&text_number=35&root=config – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005c. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *Cij “a kind of grass”

https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?root=config&basename=%2fdata%2fsintib%2fstibet&sort=proto&text_meaning=grass&ic_meaning=on&method_meaning=substring – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005d. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *cVp (~ć-) “bitter”, “pungent”

https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?root=config&basename=%2fdata%2fsintib%2fstibet&sort=proto&text_meaning=bitter&ic_meaning=on&method_meaning=substring – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005e. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *rě “rope”
https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fDATA%2fSINTIB%2fSTIBET&text_number=682&root=config – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005f. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *rěw(H) “heat”, “burn”
https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fDATA%2fSINTIB%2fSTIBET&text_number=699&root=config – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005g. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *sīr(H) “yellow”
https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fdata%2fsintib%2fstibet&text_number=1541&root=config – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005h. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *tār (~ d-) “a kind of cloth”
https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fdata%2fsintib%2fstibet&text_number=901&root=config – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005i. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *th(r)Vŋ (~ dh-) “clear”, “pure”
https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fdata%2fsintib%2fstibet&text_number=1066&root=config – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005j. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *TŋH “green”, “black”
https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fdata%2fsintib%2fstibet&text_number=2722&root=config – accessed May 2026

Starostin S. A. 2005k. Sino-Tibetan etymology database. Proto-Sino-Tibetan *ʔwŋj “blood”
https://starlingdb.org/cgi-bin/response.cgi?single=1&basename=%2fDATA%2fSINTIB%2fSTIBET&text_number=2017&root=config – accessed May 2026

Wikipedia 2026a. Attus アットウシ <https://ja.wikipedia.org/wiki/アットウシ> – accessed May 2026

Wikipedia 2026b. Picrasma quassioides https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Picrasma_quassioides – accessed May 2026

Wikipedia 2026c. Sumerian language https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sumerian_language – accessed May 2026

Wiktionary 2026. Reconstruction:Proto-Indo-European/*h₁rewd^h*

<https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/Reconstruction:Proto-Indo-European/h₁rewd^h-> – accessed May 2026